

An improved method for the determination of chloride in iron ore, coal, coke, mill sludge, flue dust and sinter products by turbidimetry and validation of results obtained by indirect atomic absorption spectrophotometry

S. K. Pradhan, P. K. Tarafder*, R. Thakur and S. Roychowdhary

Chemistry Laboratory, Regional Center for Exploration and Research, Atomic Minerals Directorate, Eastern Region, AMD Complex, Khasmahal, Jamshedpur-831 002, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : ptarafder@sify.com

Abstract : An improved and rapid procedure for the determination of chloride in iron ore, mill sludge, coal, coke, flue dust and sinter products etc. has been developed by turbidimetry, and the results obtained were validated by indirect atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) method. Chloride in these samples were leached by 10% (v/v) nitric acid and then determined by the above two methods. A correlation curve was plotted between the results obtained by the two methods, representing the efficacy of the proposed method vis-à-vis the AAS method. The correlation coefficient of the linear regression was 0.98, demonstrating that both the methods are complementary to each other.

The different experimental parameters such as choice of leaching agent, leaching time, effects of diverse ions, concentration of nitric acid etc. were studied in detail. The accuracy of the method was ascertained by estimating chloride content in some Certified Reference Materials (CRM) like Syenite sample (SY/3) and iron ore sample (BAM No. ECRM 687-1). The chloride values obtained for the CRMs were in excellent agreement with the recommended values, indicating that the method yielded fairly accurate results. The detection limit was found 0.05 µg/ml (based on mean plus 3 times standard deviation of blank, n = 5) while the RSD was found in the range 1-3% depending on the concentration of the analyte.

The advantages of the proposed method are a spectrophotometer has been used for turbidity measurement in terms of absorbance in line with turbidimetric measurement of sulphate ion and HNO₃ has been used for leaching of chloride in stead of hot water.

Keywords : Chloride, turbidimetry, atomic absorption spectrometry.

Introduction

Iron ores are rocks and minerals from which metallic iron can be economically extracted. The iron ores are usually rich in iron-oxides and are used to make pig iron, which is one of the main raw materials to make steel¹. Chloride is the most important ion while considering the possibility of pitting corrosion of stainless steel. It is generally accepted that the risk of pitting increases with increasing chloride concentration. There are also indications that higher sulphate/chloride ionic ratio is needed to inhibit the pitting corrosion of stainless steel at higher chloride concentration². Hence, determination of chloride in iron ore and other related products is very much essential for iron and other allied industries.

Recently, a few iron ore samples including mill sludge,

coal, coke, flue dust and sinter products etc. were received in our laboratory from Tata Steel, Jamshedpur for the estimation of chloride content. A lot of difficulties were faced in dissolving iron ore and other related products into a suitable medium during chloride determination. The dissolution of these samples in hydrochloric acid medium was ruled out due to obvious reason. Other mineral acids and fusion with different salt like Na₂O₂, Na₂CO₃, K₂SO₄ etc. have been tried to dissolve the samples, but due to high content of iron, these could not dissolve the samples completely. Hence, preparation of a homogeneous solution of iron ore and related products as a pre-requisite for chloride determination was a difficult task.

From literature survey³, it is revealed that iron ores

contain chloride in traces (in the range of 70–1000 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and it is present mostly in adsorbed phase. This adsorbed chloride is leachable in water using various leaching agents like H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , H_3PO_4 , Na_2CO_3 , Na_2O_2 , etc., including hot water. HNO_3 has been found to be the most suitable leaching agent because of its several advantages like strong oxidizing property and formation of highly soluble nitrate salts. Moreover, the nitrate medium facilitates turbidimetric determination of chloride⁴. However, water soluble chloride in natural iron ores, concentrates and agglomerates including sinter products have been reported³.

Over the years, numerous analytical methods for chloride determination in a variety of samples have been developed, such as Mohr⁴ titration, Volhard⁴ titration, turbidimetry⁵, coulometric⁶ titration, flow injection potentiometric⁷ titration, mercury thiocyanate-iron spectrophotometric⁸ method, Ion-chromatography⁹, resonance light scattering¹⁰, ion selective electrode¹¹, atomic absorption spectrophotometry (indirect method)¹² etc. Difficulties in measuring chloride ion by ISE methods are its proneness to variation of temperature causing fluctuation of measured voltage and treatment of electrode surface may bring about significant influence on the determination of chloride ion. The mercury thiocyanate method, commonly employed in most spectrophotometric techniques for chloride determination is avoided due to toxicity of the reagent. Mohr titration method for chloride determination suffers from low sensitivity and is applied in neutral medium only. Little deviation of pH, results into titration error. Moreover, in this pH, iron gets precipitated causing difficulty in the detection of end point. Although Volhard titration takes place in nitric acid medium, however at very strong nitric acid ($> 1.5\text{ M}$) medium, the formation of the thiocyanate-iron(III) complex $[\text{FeSCN}]^{2+}$ is rather slow and at the same time higher temperature ($> 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) tends to bleach the color of the indicator. Other potentiometric titration methods have similar disadvantages as found with that using ISE.

On the other hand, turbidimetric method is based on the measurement of the turbidity caused by silver chloride precipitation. The formation of AgCl(s) particles may be ascribed to the higher electrostatic attraction between Ag^+ and Cl^- than that of the co-existent NO_3^- ion, and it is very stable for several minutes. Though this method

has not found wide applications for determination of chloride, but as experienced by us, this method is very fast, and gives precise and accurate results.

Atomic absorption spectrophotometric method for chloride determination is, *inter-alias*, having several advantages i.e. the method is highly sensitive and precise but estimation of chloride using this method is tardy and time consuming. The results obtained by the proposed method were compared with those obtained by the indirect-AAS method and they are comparable.

Depending on the nature of samples, the turbidimetric method has been found to be most suitable for application to these types of samples, and modified/improved accordingly i.e. leaching of chloride by 10% HNO_3 (v/v) acid instead of fusing the samples with Na_2CO_3 and Na_2O_2 or hot water leaching. The present paper encompasses the details of systematic studies on the development of a modified/improved turbidimetric method for chloride determination in iron ores, coal, coke, mill sludge, flue dust and sinter products.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

An Analytik Jena, Germany make (Model : SPECORD 250+), double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer controlled by a computer with 1 cm path length quartz cell was used for turbidimetric measurement of chloride at $\lambda = 400\text{ nm}$.

Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (Model : ZEE nit 700) of the same make was used for the measurement of the absorbance of silver (indirect method for determination of chloride). Silver Hollow Cathode Lamp (HCL) was used for light source, wavelength 338.3 nm, spectral band pass 0.2 nm, lamp current 4 mA and deuterium background correction mode were applied.

Standard solution and reagents :

Alfa Aesar' make Specpure[®] standard solution of silver (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in 5% HNO_3 was used as a standard stock solution. The working standard solutions (1–5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared by diluting the standard stock solution with triple distilled water.

Standard stock solution of chloride (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was prepared by dissolving required amounts of sodium chloride (GR, Merck, Germany) in 1% (v/v) nitric acid after dried at 105 $^\circ\text{C}$ for one hour in an electric oven and

cooled in a desiccator. The working standard solutions (1–10 µg/ml) were prepared by diluting the standard stock solution with triple distilled water.

Unless otherwise stated, all reagents used were of analytical grade/guaranteed grade of standard make.

Procedure :

(i) *Preparation of sample solution :*

A 1.0 g powdered sample (mesh : -200) was taken in a 250 ml beaker and treated with 100 ml 10% (v/v) nitric acid. The mixture was digested over hot plate for about 30 min with occasional stirring. The solution was cooled and then filtered in a 100 ml volumetric flask through a filter paper (Whatman No. 540) and diluted with triple distilled water up to the mark and mixed well. This solution was used for instrumental measurement.

(ii) *Procedure for turbidimetric measurement of chloride :*

A 10 ml of sample solution was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and one pinch (approx. 0.1 g) of silver nitrate(s) was added to it. The solution was mixed gently and the resultant turbidity, in the form of absorbance, was measured at 400 nm. A series of standard chloride solution (1 to 5 µg/ml) and blank were also processed in the similar way. The concentration of chloride in sample solution was found out from a calibration curve (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Calibration curve : chloride concentration (mg/L) vs absorbance (turbidity) in spectrophotometry.

(iii) *Procedure for flame-AAS measurement of silver :*

An aliquot of sample solution containing 0.5 to 5.0 mg of chloride was placed in a 200 ml volumetric flask. A 20 ml of 1000 mg/L silver solution and 1 ml chloride free nitric acid were added to it and the solution was diluted with triple distilled water up to the mark. The solution contains 100 mg/L Ag and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight in a dark place to prevent photolysis of the solution. An aliquot of the supernatant liquid slurry was centrifuged for 3 min. 10 ml of this clear solution was taken and diluted to 100 ml in a volumetric flask. A series of calibration standards containing 0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 5.0, 7.5, 10.0 mg/L Ag were also prepared and four replicate absorbance readings of the sample and standard solutions were measured. The concentration of excess silver in sample solution was found out from a calibration curve of silver (Fig. 2). The chloride concentration was calculated in the following way.

Amount of chloride in = [{concentration of excess silver (mg/L)} × 0.329 × volume (ml)] / 1000 sample solution (mg)

Concentration of chloride in sample (µg/g) = amount of chloride in solution (mg/L) × dilution factor.

Calibration Curve: Concentration of Silver (mg/L) vs Absorbance

Fig. 2. Calibration curve : concentration of silver (mg/L) vs absorbance in Flame-AAS.

Results and discussion

Choice of leaching agent :

Several workers^{3,13} had reported soluble chloride in iron ore samples by different leaching agent. We, in our

laboratory, had tried to dissolve the sample by conventional acid digestion (HF+HNO₃) as well as fusion with alkali salts such as sodium peroxide, sodium carbonate methods. But some of the samples were not dissolved completely by any one of dissolution methods due to high content of iron. These sample solutions were filtered and the filtrates were kept for chloride determination. The acid soluble chloride was leached by different acids such as H₂SO₄, HNO₃, H₃PO₄, CH₃COOH etc. Amongst these, most satisfactory results (maximum leaching of chloride) were obtained from dilute nitric acid. Chlorides determined in different filtrates obtained from sodium carbonate and sodium peroxide fusion as well as nitric acid digestion were compared (Table 3) and it was found that nitric acid digestion yielded best leaching for chloride ion in iron ore and related samples. Chloride determined by sodium peroxide and sodium carbonate fusion yielded inconsistent results compared to those obtained by nitric acid digestion. Hence, nitric acid digestion method for leaching chloride from iron ore and related samples was adopted for chloride estimation in the above samples.

Effects of nitric acid concentration :

A series of nitric acid concentrations ranging from 0% to 15% (v/v) were used for leaching studies of chloride in iron ore and related samples. It was found that maximum chloride was leached at 8% nitric acid (v/v) and above. Hence, we optimized 10% nitric acid (v/v) for leaching of chloride from the samples.

Effects of time for leaching :

Leaching studies were carried out over a period of 5 to 60 min. The leaching of chloride was complete when the sample was digested with 10% (v/v) nitric acid for a period of 20 min. Hence, we optimized 30 min as leaching time.

Effects of foreign ions :

Many cations and anions are also present in the nitric acid leach liquor of the samples studied. For the determination of chloride in these solutions, the interference of some commonly associated ions such as Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻ etc. were investigated thoroughly under the similar conditions. CO₃²⁻

Table 1. Effect of diverse ions on the determination of 5.0 µg ml⁻¹ chloride
(Absorbance of 5.0 µg ml⁻¹ Cl⁻ in the absence of any interfering ions = 0.210)

Sl. No.	Ions added	Salt used (free from chloride)	Conc. of the ions added (µg ml ⁻¹)	Absorbance at 400 nm	Change in absorbance (%)
1.	Na ⁺	NaNO ₃	1000	0.212	0.95
2.	K ⁺	KNO ₃	1000	0.211	0.47
3.	Ca ²⁺	CaCO ₃	1000	0.213	1.42
4.	Mg ²⁺	Mg(NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	1000	0.212	0.95
5.	Fe ²⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ .FeSO ₄ .6H ₂ O	1000	0.213	1.42
6.	Al ³⁺	Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	1000	0.213	1.42
7.	SO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₄	500	0.215	2.38
8.	CO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ CO ₃	500	0.213	1.42
9.	PO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₃ PO ₄	500	0.214	1.90
10.	SO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₃	500	0.214	1.90

Table 2. Recovery studies of chloride by proposed method for SY/3 and ECRM 687-1, (n = 4)

Reference standards	Chloride (µg/g) found by proposed method	Reported value (µg/g)	% of deviation
SY/3	155	150	(+) 3.3
ECRM 687-1	165	173	(-) 4.6

ions was destroyed during hot acid digestion by dilute nitric acid treatment. The interference of SO₄²⁻, and PO₄³⁻ in excess of 100 fold concentrations to chloride ion influenced the turbidity of AgCl(s) particles. This may be due to the formation of extended aggregate around AgCl(s) particles cores by the relatively higher negatively charged ions of SO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻. Chromate interference was mini-

Table 3. The chloride concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in iron ore samples by turbidimetric method using different leaching agent, ($n = 4$)

Sl. no.	Sample ID JCL No.	Nature of sample	Chloride (Cl) content ($\mu\text{g/g}$) using 10% HNO_3	Chloride (Cl) content ($\mu\text{g/g}$) using Na_2CO_3 fusion	Chloride (Cl) content ($\mu\text{g/g}$) using Na_2O_2 fusion
1.	L 587	Coal	375	351	470
2.	L 588	Coke	69	79	105
3.	L 589	Flue Dust	406	419	568
4.	L 590	Iron Ore fines-Joda	94	100	152
5.	L 591	Iron Ore fines-Blended	87	95	125
6.	L 592	LD Sludge	281	260	405
8.	L 594	Mill Sludge	175	169	285
9.	L 595	Mill Sludge	506	466	856
10.	L 596	Iron Ore	81	89	100
11.	L 597	Sinter SP3	56	62	120
12.	L 598	Sinter SP4	31	40	103
13.	L 599	Sinter SP2	56	60	95
14.	L 600	Iron Ore Pellet	50	56	1711
15.	L 601	Iron Ore	50	54	2599
16.	L 602	ESP Dust-SP#3	356	403	1903
17.	L 603	ESP Dust-SP#3	187	177	1200

mized under the dilute acid conditions. Other ions hardly interfered with the AgCl system (Table 1). The tolerance levels of the interference of these co-existing ions in the sample solutions were very high and the assays were performed without removing them.

Validation of results :

Due to wide variation of matrix composition, the results obtained by the proposed method were found to be favourably comparable with those obtained by indirect-AAS method. By turbidimetry, the chloride determined

Table 4. The chloride concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in iron ore samples determined by two different methods, ($n = 4$)

Sl. no.	Sample ID JCL No.	Nature of sample	Chloride (Cl) content ($\mu\text{g/g}$) by turbidimetric method	Chloride (Cl) content ($\mu\text{g/g}$) by Flame-AAS method
1.	L 587	Coal	375	347
2.	L 588	Coke	69	58
3.	L 589	Flue Dust	406	440
4.	L 590	Iron Ore fines-Joda	94	95
5.	L 591	Iron Ore fines-Blended	87	80
6.	L 592	LD Sludge	281	285
7.	L 593	Mill Scale	56	43
8.	L 594	Mill Sludge	175	163
9.	L 595	Mill Sludge	506	522
10.	L 596	Iron Ore	81	86
11.	L 597	Sinter SP3	56	52
12.	L 598	Sinter SP4	31	31
13.	L 599	Sinter SP2	56	43
14.	L 600	Iron Ore Pellet	50	40
15.	L 601	Iron Ore	50	40
16.	L 602	ESP Dust-SP#3	356	352
17.	L 603	ESP Dust-SP#3	187	170

were in the range of 31–506 $\mu\text{g/g}$ whereas, it was in the range of 31–522 $\mu\text{g/g}$ by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Table 4). A correlation (scatter plot) was represented (Fig. 3) in order to evaluate the comparability of the results obtained by the two different methods. The correlation coefficient of the linear regression was 0.98, indicating that both the methods are complementary to each other.

Fig. 3. Scatter plot of iron ore samples chloride concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$) as determined by turbidimetry and Flame-AAS (indirect) method.

Precision and accuracy :

The precision of the method is about 1 to 3% as RSD ($n = 4$). Most of the samples having chloride at ppm level. The accuracy of the method was ascertained by estimating chloride content in some Certified Reference Materials (CRM) like syenite sample (SY/3) and iron ore sample (BAM No. ECRM 687-1). The chloride values obtained for the CRMs were in excellent agreement with the recommended values, indicating that the method yields fairly accurate results (Table 2).

Application to samples :

The proposed method has been applied to the determination of acid soluble chloride in a series of few iron ore samples of diverse matrices received from R&D Center, Tata Steel, Jamshedpur, India. The results are given in Table 4.

Conclusions

The proposed turbidimetry method has several advantages. The acid soluble chloride in iron ore and related samples can be easily leached by digestion with 10% nitric acid (v/v) which is the best favorable condition for its instrumental measurements. This method is very sensitive, rapid and precise.

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